

Breeding methods

Influence of type of vessel on regeneration of rice anther calli

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We studied the effect of type of vessel on regeneration of anther-derived calli of three F₁ hybrids from temperate japonica varieties.

The panicles were pretreated at 8-10°C for 7 d. The excised anthers were cultured in the dark on N₆ medium that was solidified with 4.5 g agarose/liter, 2 mg (4-chloro-2 methylphenoxy) acetic acid/liter and 60 g sucrose/liter. After 4-6 wk, we

transferred the calli for regeneration to either 90-mm-diameter disposable petri dishes or to glass jam jars of the same diameter and 0.5-liter capacity. Fourteen calli were placed in each container on 10 ml of MS medium with 2 mg kinetin/liter, 0.5 mg NAA/liter, and 40 g sucrose/liter under high light intensity.

We noted more regenerated green plants in jam jars for all the tested genotypes. The ratio of albino to green plants remained unchanged although the number of albino plants increased.

The increase in air volume in the vessel improves the regeneration rate (see table) by acting as a thermal buffer that limits the internal heating of the vessel's atmosphere under high light intensity or by permitting only a slow modification of the atmosphere inside the jar.

Calli produce ethylene and carbon dioxide. Their simultaneous presence at high concentration is unfavorable to

Rice anther callus regeneration in 2 types of vessels.

Vessel	Calli transferred to regeneration medium (no.)	Plant regeneration efficiency (%) ^d
<i>Rea/M164</i>		
Petri dishes	210	4.8 a
Glass jam jars	252	7.9 a
<i>Rea/Cristallava HI</i>		
Petri dishes	238	9.2 a
Glass jam jars	294	17.0 b
<i>Lido/Miara</i>		
Petri dishes	748	1.2 a
Glass jam jars	728	4.7 b
Total		
Petri dishes	1196	3.4 a
Glass jam jars	1274	8.7 b

^a Comparison of proportions with χ^2 at 1 df. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

organogenesis in rice. The concentration of these gases builds slowly in larger vessels. □

Yield potential

Agrophysiological differences between deepwater rice (DWR) and rainfed lowland modern variety (MV) under farmers' field conditions

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We conducted a survey under farmers' field conditions to identify the characters that explain the difference in yield potential between DWR and rainfed lowland MVs.

Twenty 9-m² plots for both the traditional DWR variety Laki and the rainfed lowland MV BR11 were selected at random within a 5-km radius of BRRI, Habiganj. Sampling was at flowering and maturity stages. The climate at flowering was similar for both varieties.

Laki yielded about 2 t grain/ha and BR11, 4 t/ha (see table). Laki produced 10 t total biomass/ha and BR11, 8 t/ha. The harvest index of Laki was less than

Some agrophysiological characteristics of BR11 and Laki under farmers' field conditions.

Character	BK11	Laki	t-test ^a
Grain yield (t/ha)	4.0 ± 0.45	1.95 ± 0.45	13.12**
Panicles (no./m ²)	207 ± 28	127 ± 28	8.75**
Filled grain (no./panicle)	102 ± 19	74 ± 11	5.72**
Sterile grain (%)	21.5	21.7	
1,000-grain wt (g)	24 ± 1	25 ± 0.8	
Straw yield (t/ha)	4.27 ± .70	7.97 ± 2.3	6.36**
Harvest index	0.48 ± .04	0.20 ± 0.04	22.49**
Sink:source (mg/cm ²)	37	28	
Leafarea (cm ² /m ²)	17.480	10.678	7.13**
Leaf area (cm ² /tiller)	113.5 ± 19	111.5 ± 17	
Specific leaf weight (mg/cm ²)	4.39 ± 0.31	4.61 ± 0.29	1.79 ^{ns}
N content (%)	2.22 ± 0.18	1.73 ± 0.10	

^a Significant at 1% level (**). ^{ns} = nonsignificant.

half that of BR11. Panicles/m² and filled grains/panicle were significantly lower in Laki than in BR11. These characters limit grain yield in Laki. Sink-source ratio was also lower in Laki. The 1,000-grain weight and sterility percentage were similar in both varieties.

The two varieties showed large differences in leaf area/m² and N content of leaves. The smaller leaf area/m² of Laki was possibly due to its lower panicle density. N content of Laki was below the critical level; that of BR11 was above the critical level for leaf photosynthesis in MVs.

Both photosynthetic capacity and ability are limiting in Laki. These observations indicate that both sink and source prevent Laki from obtaining high grain yield. □

Surveys of disease or insect incidence/severity in one environment are useful only if the information is related to other variables (e.g., climatic factors, crop intensification, cultivars, management practices, etc.). By itself, information on incidence in one environment does not increase scientific knowledge.